

The Influence of Price, Promotion, Service Quality on Satisfaction with the Decision of Selecting Anindya Bhakti Vocational School as Mediation

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Abstract:- Study This mean for investigate and analyze How factors like price, promotion, and quality service can impact on satisfaction consumer when chose Anindya Bhakti Vocational School as the mediator. Study done with use method associative causal and tool quantitative. 180 Parents student used as sample, and a side-purposive non- probability sampling method was applied. Device soft smartPLS SEM (Partial Least Square - Structural Equation Modeling) version 3.0 was used for processing research data. According to findings research, decision influenced in a manner positively and significantly by price, promotion, and quality. Price, advertising and quality service everything in a manner significant and profitable influence satisfaction. Determination Price, Promotion, and quality service everything affect choice with positive and important way.

Keywords:- Price, Promotion, Quality Service, Satisfaction and Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ Research Background

One of the most important elements in building a nation is ensuring that everyone has access to education. Education is currently one of the government's main priorities in national development. National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003 which mandates that the government uphold the rights of citizens to quality

education reflects this. The availability of human resources who can be trusted to carry out the development process is a component that greatly determines the success of the process. A person's knowledge increases with their level of education, which has an impact on their wages or income. Through education, we can fight country's economic success.

The Covid-19 pandemic provides significant impact to field education, for one is decline amount student new enrollees, especially at school _ private. Economy nation Not yet capable stop pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic, according to Sri Mulyani, Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia, caused Indonesia's economy experienced contraction in the second quarter of 2020 which resulted in a decline in real GDP.

The number of people living in poverty in Indonesia has increased to 26.42 million, according to the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS). According to data from the Central Statistics Agency for Banten Province, the poverty rate for Banten Province as reported by the National Socio-Economic Survey (Susenas) in March 2020 was 5.92%, up 0.98 percentage points from the same period the previous year (September 2019), or 4.49%. This is in line with the increase in the number of poor people from September 2019 to March 2020 of 134,6000 people, from 641.42,000 to 775.99,000. Due to the increase in fuel prices, there has been an increase in both the number and percentage of poor people over the years. Meanwhile, in March 2020.

Fig 1 Development of poverty in Banten

Source: Central Statistics Agency for Banten Province 2021

The government is obliged to provide education which is a very important factor in a person's life cycle from birth to death (Long Life Education). Education is conceptually conscious work and its aim is to advance the life and development of the nation. The following is the number of public and private schools in Tangerang City.

Table 1 Development of the Number of Public and Private Vocational Schools in the City Tangerang

No	Tangerine City	Owner/Manager		Amount
		State Vocational High School	Private Vocational High School	
1	district Ciledug		12	12
2	district Cinpodoh		19	19
3	district Tangerang	4	18	22
4	district Teak Uwung		4	4
5	district Flatstone		9	9
6	district Object		4	4
7	district Prohibition		4	4
8	district Central Reef		4	4
9	district betel nut	1	12	13
10	district Karawaci	1	14	15
11	district Cibodas	1	4	5
12	district Pot	1	10	11
13	district Neglasari	1	8	9

Source: Tangerang City Education Office, 2021

From the table above, it can be seen that the number of State Vocational High Schools owned by the Tangerang City Government is only 9 schools and Private Vocational High Schools as many as 122 schools.

Table 2 Development of the Number of State and Private SMKs in Karawaci District, Tangerang City

No	SMK School	Subdistrict	Address
1	AL- Ijtihad Vocational High School	Karawaci	Jl. Al-Ijtihad No. 1, Kec. Karawaci Banten 15113
2	Citra Nusantara Vocational High School	Karawaci	JL. Arya Wangsakara N0. 1 nude
3	Buddhist High School	Karawaci	JL. Imam Bonjol N0 41 Karawaci
4	SMKN 7 Tangerang	Karawaci	JL. Sangego Raya Watergate 10
5	SMKS Bhakti Pertiwi	Karawaci	JL. Good Night Perumanas Nusajaya
6	Voctech 1st Vocational High School	Karawaci	JL. Raya Prolamaksi No. 55 Cimone
7	Strada Daan Mogot Vocational School	Karawaci	JL. Plot Surya RT 02/06 Pabuaran Karawaci
5	Archipelago 1st Vocational High School	Karawaci	JL. Cisadane VIII Perumnas I Nusajaya
6	PGRI 109 PRIVATE VOCATIONAL SCHOOL	Karawaci	JL. Untung Suropati II NO. 14 Cimone Jaya
7	Nusa Putra Vocational High School	Karawaci	JL. Teuku Umar No. 12 Nusajaya

Source: Data Processed by Researchers, 2022

The table above shows the location of schools in Karawaci District, Tangerang City, including AL Ijtihad Vocational School, Citra Nusantara Vocational School, Buddhi Vocational School , Tangerang 7 Vocational School , Bhakti Pertiwi Vocational School, Voctech 1 Vocational School Tangerang, Strada Daan Mogot Vocational School, Nusantara 1 Vocational School Tangerang, PGRI 109 Vocational High School Tangerang , SMKS Nusa Putra.

Fig 2 Number of Students at SMK Bhakti Anindya Tangerang City
Source: Bhakti Vocational School Self-processed, 2022

From the data shown, it can be seen that the number of students attending SMK Bhakti Anindya in 2019 totaled 353 students and in 2020 there has been a decrease in the number of students to 328 students and in 2021 there has been a decrease of 189 students.

Table 3 Statement on Pre-Survey

Variable	Question	YES	No
Brand Image	SMK Bhakti Aninyda is a school with a name that is easy to pronounce.	35 %	65 %
Location	Distance between Bhakti Anindya Vocational School with House INo Far.	25 %	75 %
Price	The costs incurred are in accordance with the benefits I receive.	90%	10 %
Promotion	I got information from Anindya Bhakti Vocational School media promotion House Sick(media print and electronic).	75 %	15 %
Quality Service	Teachers and Administration have good knowledge, skills, abilities and expertise in serving me.	70 %	30%

Source: Data Pre-Survey, 2022

Based on the results of the survey on the highest "Yes" answers, it can be concluded that customer opinions are as follows: X Parents feel that teachers and administrators have good knowledge, skills, abilities and expertise in serving. The costs that parents have to incur are commensurate with the benefits received and Parents of students can find out information about SMK Bhakti Anindya through promotional media for SMK Bhakti Anindya that they encounter (print and electronic media).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ Price

The amount of money determined by counting or evaluating the purchase, use of a commodity, or service is what Kotler and Armstrong (2017) define as "price".

The entire value of an item or service, or the amount of money obtained from the total value of an item or service, is what consumers exchange for price benefits, according to Philip Kotler Indrasari's book (2019). This is an important component.

➤ Promotion

Sales promotion, according to Kotler and Armstrong (2017), is an action that conveys the advantages of a product and encourages buyers to buy it.

Kotler and Keller stated in Aji (2019) that sales promotion is a component of a marketing strategy, where promotions directly or indirectly educate, influence, and remind consumers about the products being sold. Promotion is a type of marketing communication that includes activities such as spreading knowledge, influencing or persuading the public, and reminding them about a company or its products so that they are ready to accept, buy and accept the products offered by these companies so that they are loyal to them. The companies in question are those involved in these marketing activities (Musfar, 2020).

➤ Quality Service

The ability of a product or service to satisfy stated or a priori desires is influenced by various qualities and attributes, according to Kotler and Keller (2012).

According to Tjiptono in Sondakh (2014), service quality involves managing these benefits to meet customer expectations while maintaining the required level of excellence. Expected service and perceived service both have an impact on service quality.

Tjiptono cites Sondakh's statement (2014) that when the service obtained or experienced (perceived service) meets expectations, then service quality is considered good and satisfying, but if it exceeds customer expectations, it is perfect quality. Conversely, services with poorer projected reception performance are perceived as having poor service quality. However, whether a service is good or bad depends on the ability of the service provider to continue to meet the expectations of its clients.

➤ Consumer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction according to Homer in Indrasari (2019: 82) is the degree to which consumers feel after comparing what they receive with what they anticipate. Indrasari (2019: 82), with contributions from Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, defines consumer satisfaction as a person's reaction to the performance (outcome) of a product in relation to expectations.

➤ Buying Decision

Purchase choice is one of the stages in the buying decision process that appears before post-purchase behavior, according to Arafah (2022:04). Consumers have reached a stage of the buying decision process in which they are presented with a number of different alternatives. At this point, consumers decide to buy products according to the choices made.

Kotler and Armstrong define consumer behavior as the study of how people, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and how products, services, ideas, or experiences meet their needs and wants. This definition is found in Gunawan (2022: 10).

Fig 3 Thinking Framework
Source Processed: Researchers (2022)

III. SURVEY METHOD

A. Research Design

In this study, quantitative research was used along with survey techniques and explanatory strategies. According to Sugiyono (2017: 11), the quantitative method can be understood as a research methodology based on a positivist school of thought, used for research on certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, and the purpose of testing a pre-existing hypothesis.

B. Population and Sample

➤ **Research Population**

Sugiyono (2021) defines population as a broad category consisting of objects or individuals with certain attributes and characteristics that have been found through research to be examined in order to reach conclusions. The target of this research is the students' parents. The population of this study were 200 respondents who were parents of SMK Bhakti Anindya students.

➤ **Sample**

Sugiyono claims that the sample reflects the size and characteristics of the population. If the population is large enough and the researcher cannot investigate every member of the population, for example due to lack of resources (money, manpower and time), the researcher can use a sample from the population. 2018 (Sugiyono) Because this research design uses 28 indicators, the number of samples determined in this study is at least 140.

The criteria for the number of research samples that must be collected are modified to suit the criteria for the number of samples that must be used for Structural Equation

Modeling (SEM) studies. According to Hair et al., the use of SEM allows the simultaneous investigation of a number of correlations to provide statistical efficiency. Hair et al. guidelines for determining the size of the sample size for SEM are given as follows:

- A sample size between 100 and 200 is recommended for parameter estimation using the maximum likelihood estimation approach, with a minimum sample size of 50.
- Up to 5 to 10 times more parameters than in the model.
- Equal to 5 to 10 times the sum of all manifest variables (indicators). (2014) Hair et al.
- Because there are 28 indications in this study, it requires 140 respondents or a minimum sample size of 5x28.

• **Method of Collecting Data**

Data collection techniques are used to collect the information needed for research. 2021 (Sugiyono)

➤ **Primary Data**

Primary data is research information that has been collected to answer certain research questions at the request of researchers and has been taken directly from the original source. The following are the main techniques for collecting data:

• **Interview**

If a researcher wants to conduct a preliminary investigation to identify a phenomenon or problem that needs to be researched, if the researcher wants to study in-depth information that can be obtained from respondents, and if the number of respondents is small or few, they will do so. using interviews as a data collection technique (Sugiyono, 2021).

The researcher has chosen the interview method to collect data by directly asking questions to the marketing team about the problem being investigated and the subject of the research.

• *Questionnaire*

By providing a list of questions or written statements to respondents to respond to, a questionnaire is a data collection method (Sugiyono, 2021).

➤ *Data Secondary*

Secondary data is a source of research data obtained indirectly by researchers or through other parties. Secondary data is usually in the form of evidence, historical records or reports that have been compiled in archives (documents) that can be published or cannot be published. As for method Which done in engineering data retrieval secondary as following:

- *Library Research (Library Research)*
- *Research journal*
- *Internet*

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION FROM RESULTS

➤ *Testing Average Variance Extracted*

The AVE (Average Variance Extracted) test requirement which further supports the findings of convergent validity states that the concept used in the study is valid if the AVE value is > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2019). Below are the results of various mean-variance tests run using the PLS 3.0 tool.

Table 4 Average Variance Extracted Values

Latent	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	R Critical	Criteria (AVE ≥ 0.5)
Price (X1)	0.755	0.5	Valid
Promotion (X2)	0.666	0.5	Valid
Service Quality (X3)	0.727	0.5	Valid
decision (Z)	0.699	0.5	Valid
satisfaction (Y)	0.839	0.5	Valid

Source: Data Processing (2023)

It is clear that the average of the variations taken serves as the basis for the *convergent validity results*. These findings indicate that the AVE of each latent variable is more than 0.5. This shows that when viewed from the average value of the variance extract, latent construct indicators have *convergent validity* the strong one.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 5 Value of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Latent	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Price (X1)	0.892	0.925
Promotion (X2)	0.874	0.909
Service Quality (X3)	0.958	0.964
Decision (Z)	0.928	0.942
Satisfaction (Y)	0.968	0.973

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Seen that there is latent structure with Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.6, indicating that latent structure in question own good reliability. Besides that, value reliability For every construction lattice more big from 0.60. Based on model reliability test results and the Cronbach configuration used, p This show that such models own good reliability.

➤ *R Square*

Testing with Smart PLS 3., obtained the following R Square results.

Table 6 R Square

	R Square	Connection
Decision (Z)	0.763	Strong
Satisfaction (Y)	0.849	Strong

Source: Data Processing (2023)

Decisions (Z) affect satisfaction (Y) by 84.9%, according to R-square satisfaction variable (Y) that is equal to 0.849. The remaining 15.1% is influenced by other variables in the study that are not researched

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

The following are findings that can be drawn from the research and discussion that was carried out in the previous chapter concerning the Effect of Price, Promotion, and Quality on Satisfaction with the Decision to Choose Anindya Bhakti Vocational School as Mediation.

- Prices affect parents' decisions at SMK Bhakti Anindya.
- Promotion affects people's decisions senior at SMK Bhakti Anindya.
- Service quality influences people's decisions senior at SMK Bhakti Anindya.
- Price has no effect on parental satisfaction at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School.
- Promotion has no effect on parental satisfaction at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School.
- Service quality influences parental satisfaction at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School.
- The decision acts as a price mediation for parental satisfaction at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School.
- The decision acts as a mediation for the promotion of parental satisfaction at Anindya Bhakti Vocational School.
- The decision acts as a mediation of service quality on parental satisfaction at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School.
- Decisions affect parental satisfaction at SMK Bhakti Anindya.

B. Recommendation

Based on the research conducted and the conclusions above, the researcher intends to provide some suggestions to those who will use the results of this study in the future. This proposal is divided into two parts, one theoretical and one administrative, including the following:

➤ Theoretical

According to the research findings, the researchers recommend the following:

- The variables in this study such as school image, location, facilities, school accreditation, word-of mouth, and so on, can be retested in subsequent studies using other variables not discussed in this study.
- Future research can broaden the subject by including parents of children who are interested in entering Vocational High Schools and parents of students.

➤ Managerial

The study findings led the researchers to make the following recommendations:

- Regarding the suitability of the price of educational services at Bhakti Anindya Vocational School with the services provided by teachers and non-teachers, the lowest average result for the price variable was 3.86. The price that has been calculated and applied must then be

checked to determine whether it is appropriate for the services provided.

- On the promotion variable, the lowest mean value results obtained about 3.64 SMK Bhakti Anindya routinely conducts education about science in junior high schools (SMP) etc. So activity held by SMK Bhakti Anindya must be carried out regularly and more interesting.
- In the service quality variable, the lowest mean result is obtained figure 3.83 regarding Teaching staff (teachers) and non-teaching staff are alert to the needs of children. Bhakti Anindya Vocational School need increase standard criteria certain on the competence of teacher and non-teacher officers in coping complaint.
- In the satisfaction variable, the lowest mean result is obtained at 3.81 regarding the services provided by teaching staff (teachers) and non-teaching staff are satisfactory. so it is necessary to do a detailed evaluation of student development so that teachers and non-teachers can meet their needs students by precise and fast.
- In the decision variable, the lowest mean result is obtained about 3.67 parents' interest in comparing school prices with other schools. so SMK Bhakti Anindya can implement the strategy namely the steps are structured to get new students.

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